

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

**WHITE COAT HYPERTENSION – THE RISK FACTOR FOR
SUSTAINED HYPERTENSION AND CARDIOVASCULAR
DISEASE****J Vijay Kumar, Gera Jemimah, Yamuna Bonagiri, T Shravani Reddy, M Keerthana,
AVSSS Gupta**

Joginpally BR Pharmacy College, Yenkapally, Moinabad, Hyderabad, Telangana

Abstract:

White coat hypertension (WCH) is characterized by variations in the blood pressure of a person between physician's office and home environment. The presence of physician causes the elevation of blood pressure in patients with WCH, which is a clinical condition under white coat syndrome that also includes white coat effect and masked hypertension. Levels of BP values to categorize a patient as white coat hypertensive, is given by the 2013 European Society of Hypertension/European Society of Cardiology hypertension guidelines. Proper diagnosis using ambulatory blood pressure monitoring is crucial to avoid misdiagnosis and unwanted prescription of antihypertensive drugs. WCH phenomenon is associated with long-term risk of development of true hypertension, cardiovascular alterations and target organ damage. Aim of this review article is to provide information regarding epidemiology, etiology, mechanisms, diagnosis, management and clinical impact of white coat hypertension.

Key Words: White Coat Hypertension, antihypertensive drugs, White Coat Effect, Masked Hypertension, epidemiology.

Corresponding author:**Gera Jemimah,**

Joginpally BR Pharmacy College, Yenkapally

Moinabad, Hyderabad, Telangana

Mobile: 9505346133

E-mail: gerajemimah7@gmail.com

QR code

Please cite this article in press Gera Jemimah et al., *White Coat Hypertension – The Risk Factor for Sustained Hypertension and Cardiovascular Disease.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(12).

INTRODUCTION:

White coat hypertension is the term used to denote a condition in which persons not receiving antihypertensive medication, experience persistent high blood pressure levels ($\geq 140/90$ mm Hg) when measured in the presence of a physician or at a medical office, but have normal blood pressure levels during daily lives and in the home environment [1-6]. The term white coat comes from reference to the white coat traditionally worn by the doctors. White coat hypertension was first discovered by Riva-Rocci in 1896 and the term was coined by Thomas Pickering.

It is very common that BP levels are not fixed and they vary throughout the day. In certain portion of population, high BP levels were observed when obtained by a physician than that of the levels obtained by them. This difference revealed a clinical condition called "white coat syndrome." It is a common phenomenon noted in both hypertensive and normotensive individuals [7]. This syndrome comprises of 1) white coat effect (WCE), 2) white coat hypertension (WCH), and 3) white coat normotension or masked hypertension (MH) [8].

According to the 2013 European Society of Hypertension/ Society of Cardiology guidelines, white coat hypertension (WCH) is characterized when individuals without antihypertensive medication presents office systolic/diastolic blood pressure measurements of $\geq 140/90$ mm Hg on at least three occasions, but with normal ambulatory (24-hour ambulatory blood pressure $< 130/80$ mmHg) or home blood pressure (135/85 mmHg) readings [9-12]. Thus, if office reading alone was observed, patients may be wrongly characterized as hypertensives. WCH is considered as an intermediate stage between normotensive and hypertensive conditions [13].

White coat effect (WCE) is a condition where hypertensive patients treated with antihypertensives show elevated office blood pressure levels of > 20 mmHg of systolic BP and > 10 mmHg of diastolic BP in the presence of physician or health care professional, when compared to normal ambulatory or home blood pressure measurements [5, 10]. This condition may give false impression of a person being uncontrolled hypertensive and need for alteration of drug therapy, hence should be carefully evaluated. Higher heart rate and non-dipping nocturnal BP was observed with this effect [14].

Masked hypertension (MH) is considered as an inverse condition of WCH and is characterized by

adequate office blood pressure levels of $< 140/90$ mmHg, but high outside office blood pressure levels by ambulatory ($\geq 130/80$ mmHg) or home ($\geq 135/85$ mmHg) blood pressure monitoring devices [11]. MH is strongly associated with increased risk of cardiovascular diseases and target organ damage when compared to WCH [15-20].

Incorrect identification of both WCH and WCE may lead to unnecessary initiation or intensification of the antihypertensive therapy. Attention should also be given to MH as it is associated with all-cause mortality [10]. Purpose of this article is to provide information about the prevalence, etiology, mechanisms, diagnosis and clinical impact of the white coat syndrome.

EPIDEMIOLOGY

White coat hypertension accounts for 15-30% of the individuals with increased office blood pressure levels [21, 22]. 30-40% patients who are diagnosed with hypertension on the basis of office BP levels are actually white coat hypertensives [5, 23]. Prevalence of MH varies between 15-30%. The prevalence of WCH is higher in females, obese people, smokers, older adults (15-25%) and it increases with age. It also occurs more frequently in pregnant women, patients who are recently diagnosed with hypertension and in those without evidence of target organ damage [24-29].

Prevalence in India and the state of Telangana

Recently, Indian Heart Study (IHS) commissioned by Eris Life Sciences conducted study on hypertension in 15 states of India and the findings of the study were declared on August 21, 2019. The study was conducted for 9 months, nationwide in 18,918 people (64% male and 36% female) including 1168 people from the state of Telangana. Blood pressure values are recorded 4 times a day continuously for 7 days. Overall, 41% of the subjects were unaware of the fact that they had hypertension and 18% exhibited masked hypertension. The prevalence of hypertension is increasing in the state of Telangana as 36% people have white coat hypertension, 22% with hypertension and 14% have masked hypertension, due to unhealthy food habits and sedentary lifestyle [30].

ETIOLOGY

White coat hypertension is a phenomenon where increase in the blood pressure was experienced only during visit by a physician. Patient's blood pressure spiked 2-4 minutes after the start of the visit and remained high throughout the duration of the visit. Researchers indicated that the emotional factors like

stress or anxiety may be responsible for this phenomenon. White coat hypertensives have been shown to be more prone to higher anxiety levels than normotensive and persistent hypertensive individuals [31, 32]. According to previous literature, WCH is also associated with metabolic syndrome [33]. Where and by whom blood pressure is taken, also plays a role in the development of WCH [34]. MH is seen in youngsters with left ventricular hypertrophy, diabetes, and/or obesity, family history of hypertension, cardiovascular factors, and a high office BP at any moment [21].

Other reasons that can trigger white coat hypertension include recent ingestion of pressor agents, stress and emergency, sedentary lifestyle, high intake of salt and spicy food, consumption of increased amounts of caffeine, perception of having hypertension, and technical inaccuracies [30, 35].

MECHANISMS

By measuring the muscles and skin of the sympathetic nerve traffic, it was found that the anxiety or stress that led to white coat hypertension is due to pronounced activation of the skin nerves and associated sympathetic inhibition of muscle nerve-traffic [36, 37]. According to some authors, this elevation of BP is due to neuro-endocrine reflex mediated by sympathetic nervous system, which is conditioned by the anticipation of having illness during the measurement of BP [38, 39]. Sympathetic activity in WCH is determined by the levels of circulating and urinary catecholamines and renin activity.

In treated hypertensive individuals, WCH is associated with arterial stiffness. According to a study, people with WCH has worse vascular function, greater cardiovascular mortality, lower pulse wave velocity and high levels of left ventricular mass index when compared to normotensives [40-43]. White coat effect is mediated by the increased activity of sympathetic nervous system and this phenomenon may be associated with worse prognosis. Arterial ageing and impaired arterial compliance are associated with WCE [44-46]. When compared to normotensives, people with MH have thickening and lower complacency of the carotid artery. High risk of left ventricular structural alterations is associated with untreated MH individuals [47, 48].

DIAGNOSIS

Blood pressure can be assessed by many methods. For proper diagnosis of the hypertension or to modify the antihypertensive treatment, it is very important to correctly measure the blood pressure. To detect white

coat syndrome, currently two well accepted methods are available – HBPM (Home Blood Pressure Monitoring) and ABPM (Ambulatory Blood Pressure Monitoring) [8].

In HBPM method, BP can be easily measured by the individuals and is well accepted by the patients, but fluctuations in the BP during sleep period cannot be observed [3]. The best method to detect BP fluctuations is the ABPM method, which offers monitoring of BP for a period of 24 hours. This method gives more accurate diurnal and nocturnal BP measurements, determines nocturnal hypertension, evaluates the efficacy of antihypertensive therapy and is a strong predictor of cardiovascular mortality [21].

According to the Task Force of the Eighth International Consensus Conference on Blood Pressure Monitoring, white coat hypertension can be confirmed in untreated persons on the basis of ambulatory readings when office BP on three or more separate visits is $\geq 140/90$ mmHg, two or more BP readings taken outside the office are $< 140/90$ mmHg and when there is no evidence of target organ damage [49, 50].

MANAGEMENT

In short period of time, white coat hypertension can progress into sustained hypertension, especially in middle-aged and elderly people, and cardiovascular risk is increased when compared to people with normal BP values [51]. So, once white coat hypertension was confirmed by ABPM, the European Society of Hypertension recommends reconfirmation in 3-6 months and yearly follow-up to detect any evidence of sustained hypertension/ true hypertension, as there is a risk of developing it [21, 52].

Resistant hypertensives demonstrated white coat hypertension, so it is recommended that the medication should not be given to patients who start to develop mild or moderate high blood pressure unless there is target organ damage and BP remains high even after 3-6 visits [53, 54]. According to 2013 European Society of Hypertension/European Society of Cardiology hypertension guidelines, WCH patients with no additional cardiovascular risk factors are to be treated with lifestyle changes and should have a close follow-up. Also, WCH patients with increased cardiovascular risk due to metabolic abnormalities or asymptomatic target organ damage are to be considered for antihypertensive treatment in addition to changes in the lifestyle [55].

As anxiety plays an important role in WCH, effective

communication between a physician and the patient can reduce their anxiety about the illness. It is considered as a cornerstone of good medical practice. Empathy and trust also play a crucial role in reducing the anxiety [36].

PROGNOSIS

The prognosis of the white coat hypertension is controversial. Correct diagnosis and clinical guidance are essential to improve prognosis of the patients with WCH. Even though treatment is not required, they are to be closely monitored. After a follow-up of 20 years, WCH patients are associated with impaired insulin sensitivity, increase in blood glucose, serum insulin and heart rate when compared to people with normal blood pressure. It was also found that the requirement of antihypertensive drug treatment was more frequent in patients with WCH. Incidence of cardiovascular events, mortality, aortic pulsed wave velocity, cystatin C and urinary albumin-to-creatinine ratio also increased after follow-up [56-59].

CLINICAL IMPACT

Patients with WCH have 2.5 times more chances to develop a sustained hypertension compared to normal individuals. Hence, untreated WCH is no longer considered as a harmless clinical state due to increased risk for the development of target organ damage and consequent cardiovascular damage [13]. In the group of white coat syndrome, white coat effect is considered less damaging. Development of target organ damage in patients with MH is close to the risk associated with hypertensive patients.

According to 2012 IDACO study, untreated white coat hypertension was associated with increase risk in men and persons with diabetes mellitus [60]. Risk of target organ damage increases from white coat effect to hypertension i.e., white coat effect < white coat hypertension < masked hypertension < hypertension [8]. In summary, some people with WCH progresses over time to sustained hypertension, but according to majority of studies there is no significant increase in the cardiovascular risk when compared to normotensive individuals [49].

Individuals with WCE, WCH, MH or hypertension should be carefully pursued and diagnosed to decide appropriate therapeutic intervention, as these conditions are associated with possible worsening of cardiovascular prognosis and development of target organ damage.

CONCLUSION

WCH is a common medical problem now-a-days, which occurs mostly due to anxiety in the presence of

a physician or sedentary lifestyle. This should be no longer considered as clinically innocent because of its association with metabolic abnormalities, progression to sustained hypertension in untreated individuals, increased risk of cardiovascular events and the target organ damage. At present, correct diagnosis of the WCH subjects seems to be the key step, as it can avoid unnecessary treatment with antihypertensive drugs. Clinicians should be aware that the untreated WCH patients may be at a risk of increased cardiovascular diseases. Efforts are to be made to improve patient-physician communication to reduce the anxiety. To optimize the clinical management of WCH, further studies are to be carried out to evaluate the phenomena associated with it and to provide scientific data that helps in deciding therapy needed in WCH. Correct diagnosis of white coat syndrome through ABPM and HBPM is fundamental for the therapeutic efficacy and better prognosis of the individuals with this syndrome.

REFERENCES:

1. Chobanian AV, Bakris GL, Black HR, Cushman WC, Green LA, et al. The Seventh Report of the Joint National committee on Prevention, Detection, Evaluation, and Treatment of High Blood Pressure. The JNC 7 Report. *JAMA*, 2003; 289:2560-2572.
2. Aronow WS, Fleg JL, Pepine CJ, Artinian NT, Bakris G, et al. ACCF/AHA 2011 expert consensus document on hypertension in the elderly: a report of the American College of Cardiology Foundation Task Force on Clinical Expert Consensus Documents. *J Am Coll Cardiol*, 2011; 57:2037-2114.
3. Parati G, Stergiou GS, Asmar R, Bilo G, de Leeuw P, et al. European Society of Hypertension practice guidelines for home blood pressure monitoring. *J Hum Hypertens*, 2010; 24:779-785.
4. Mancia G, Fagard R, Narkiewicz K, Redon J, Zanchetti A, et al. ESH/ESC guidelines for the management of arterial hypertension: the Task Force for the Management of Arterial Hypertension of the European Society of Hypertension (ESH) and of the European Society of Cardiology (ESC). *Eur Heart J*, 2013; 34(28):2159-2219.
5. Celis H, Fagard RH. White-coat hypertension: a clinical review. *Eur J Intern Med*, 2004; 15(6):348-357.
6. Mancia G, Bombelli M, Seravalle G, Grassi G. Diagnosis and management of patients with white-coat and masked hypertension. *Nat Rev Cardiol*, 2011; 8(12):686-693.
7. Pickering, TG. Blood pressure measurement and

- detection of hypertension. *Lancet*, 1994; 344(8914):31-35.
8. Mariana RP, Alessandra MVR, de Faria AP, Rodrigo M. White coat syndrome and its variations: differences and clinical impact. *Integrated Blood Pressure Control*, 2018; 11:73-79.
 9. Sipahioglu NT, Sipahioglu F. Closer look at white-coat hypertension. *World J Methodol*, 2014; 4(3):144-150.
 10. Whelton PK, Carey RM, Aronow WS, et al. 2018 ACC/AHA/AAPA/ABC/ACPM/AGS/APhA/ASH/ASPC/ NMA/PCNA Guideline for the Prevention, Detection, Evaluation, and Management of High Blood Pressure in Adults: A Report of the American College of Cardiology/ American Heart Association Task Force on Clinical Practice Guidelines. *Hypertension*, 2018; 71(6):1269-1324.
 11. Williams B, Mancia G, Spiering W, et al. Authors/Task Force Members. 2018 ESC/ESH Guidelines for the management of arterial hypertension: The Task Force for the management of arterial hypertension of the European Society of Cardiology (ESC) and the European Society of Hypertension (ESH). 2018; 36(10):1953-2041.
 12. Malachias MVB, Gomes MAM, Nobre F, et al. 7th Brazilian Guideline of Arterial Hypertension: Chapter 2 – Diagnosis and Classification. *Arq Bras Cardiol*, 2016; 107(3 Suppl 3):7-13. English, Portuguese.
 13. Mancia G, Bombelli M, Facchetti R, et al. Long-term risk of sustained hypertension in white-coat or masked hypertension. *Hypertension*, 2009; 54(2):226–232.
 14. Bochud M, Bovet P, Vollenweider P, et al. Association between white-coat effect and blunted dipping of nocturnal blood pressure. *Am J Hypertens*, 2009; 22(10):1054-1061.
 15. Peacock J, Diaz KM, Viera AJ, Schwartz JE, Shimbo D. Unmasking masked hypertension: prevalence, clinical implications, diagnosis, correlates and future directions. *J Hum Hypertens*, 2014; 28(9):521-528.
 16. Anstey DE, Booth JN 3rd, Abdalla M, et al. Predicted Atherosclerotic Cardiovascular Disease Risk and Masked Hypertension among Blacks in the Jackson Heart Study. *Circ Cardiovasc Qual Outcomes*, 2017; 10(7):e003421.
 17. Asayama K, Thijs L, Li Y, et al. International Database on Ambulatory Blood Pressure in Relation to Cardiovascular Outcomes (IDACO) Investigators. Setting thresholds to varying blood pressure monitoring intervals differentially affects risk estimates associated with white-coat and masked hypertension in the population. *Hypertension*, 2014, 64(5):935-942.
 18. Fagard RH, Cornelissen A. Incidence of cardiovascular events in white-coat, masked and sustained hypertension versus true normotension: a meta-analysis. *J Hypertens*, 2007; 25(11):2193-2198.
 19. Banegas JR, Ruilope LM, de la Sierra A, et al. Relationship between Clinic and Ambulatory Blood-Pressure Measurements and Mortality. *N Engl J Med*, 2018; 378(16):1509-1520.
 20. Yoon HJ, Ahn Y, Park JB, et al. Are metabolic risk factors and target organ damage more frequent in masked hypertension than in white coat hypertension? *Clin Exp Hypertens*, 2010; 32(7):480-485.
 21. O'Brien E, Parati G, Stergiou G, et al. On behalf of the European Society of Hypertension Working Group on Blood Pressure Monitoring. European Society of Hypertension position paper on ambulatory blood pressure monitoring. *J Hypertens*, 2013; 31(9):1731-1767.
 22. O'Brien E, Coats A, Owens P, Petrie J, Padfield PL, Littler WA, de Swiet M, Mee F. Use and interpretation of ambulatory blood pressure monitoring: recommendations of the British hypertension society. *BMJ*, 2000; 320:1128-1134.
 23. Cesare Cuspidi MD, Marijana Tadic MD, Giuseppe Mancia MD, Guido Grassi MD. White-Coat Hypertension: the Neglected Subgroup in Hypertension. *Korean Circ J*, 2018; 48(7):552-564.
 24. Cuspidi C, Sala C, Grassi G, Mancia G. White coat hypertension: to treat or not to treat? *Curr Hypertens Rep*, 2016;18(11):80.
 25. Dolan E, Stanton A, Atkins N, et al. Determinants of white-coat hypertension. *Blood Press Monit*, 2004; 9(6):307-309.
 26. Fisher M, Blackwell J, Saseen J. What is the best way to identify patients with white-coat hypertension? *J Fam Pract*, 2005; 54(6):549-550.
 27. Verdecchia P, Palatini P, Schillaci G, Mormino P, Porcellati C, Pessina AC. Independent predictors of isolated clinic ('white-coat') hypertension. *J Hypertens*, 2001; 19(6):1015-1020.
 28. Manios ED, Koroboki EA, Tsvigoulis GK, et al. Factors influencing white-coat effect. *Am J Hypertens*, 2008; 21(2):153-158.
 29. Manios ED, Koroboki EA, Tsvigoulis GK, Spengos KM, Spiliopoulou IK, et al. Factors influencing white-coat effect. *Am J Hypertens*, 2008; 21:153-158.

30. Eris Life Sciences Improving Health Outcomes. 2019. Indian Heart Study (IHS) commissioned by Eris Life Sciences. Available at: <https://eris.co.in/news/india-heart-study-ihs-commissioned-by-eris-lifesciences/>
31. Grassi G, Turri C, Vailati S, Dell'Oro R, Mancia G. Muscle and skin sympathetic nerve traffic during the "white-coat" effect. *Circulation*, 1999; 100(3):222-225.
32. Ogedegbe G, Pickering TG, Clemow L, et al. The misdiagnosis of hypertension: the role of patient anxiety. *Arch Intern Med*, 2008; 168(22):2459-2465.
33. Helvacı MR, Sevinc A, Camci C, Yalcin A. Treatment of white coat hypertension with metformin. *Int Heart J*, 2008; 49(6):671-679.
34. Gerin W, Marion RM, Friedman R, James GD, Bovbjerg DH, Pickering TG. How should we measure blood pressure in the doctor's office? *Blood Press Monit*, 2001; 6(5):257-262.
35. White Coat Hypertension. 2019. Available at: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/White_coat_hypertension
36. Briana C, Haskard-Zolnierok K, Howard K. White coat hypertension: improving the patient-health care practitioner relationship. *Psychology Research and Behavior Management*, 2015; 8:133-141.
37. Grassi G, Seravalle G, Buzzi S, Magni L, Brambilla G, et al. Muscle and skin sympathetic nerve traffic during physician and nurse blood pressure measurement. *J Hypertens*, 2013; 31:1131-1135.
38. Bloomfield DA, Park, A. Decoding white coat hypertension. *World J Clin Cases*, 2017; 5(3):82-92.
39. Mancia G, Bertinieri G, Grassi G, et al. Effects of blood-pressure measurement by the doctor on patient's blood pressure and heart rate. *Lancet*, 1983; 2(8352):695-698.
40. Barochiner J, Aparicio LS, Alfie J, et al. Arterial Stiffness in Treated Hypertensive Patients With White-Coat Hypertension. *J Clin Hypertens (Greenwich)*, 2017; 19(1):6-10.
41. Sung SH, Cheng HM, Wang KL, et al. White coat hypertension is more risky than prehypertension: important role of arterial wave reflections. *Hypertension*, 2013; 61(6):1346-1353.
42. Andrikou I, Tsioufis C, Dimitriadis K, et al. Similar levels of low-grade inflammation and arterial stiffness in masked and white-coat hypertension: comparisons with sustained hypertension and normotension. *Blood Press Monit*, 2011; 16(5):218-223.
43. Androulakis E, Papageorgiou N, Lioudaki E, et al. Subclinical Organ Damage in White-Coat Hypertension: The Possible Role of Cystatin C. *J Clin Hypertens (Greenwich)*, 2017; 19(2):190-197.
44. Cuspidi C, Meani S, Salerno M, et al. Cardiovascular target organ damage in essential hypertensives with or without reproducible nocturnal fall in blood pressure. *J Hypertens*, 2004; 22(2):273-280.
45. de Simone G, Schillaci G, Chinali M, et al. Estimate of white-coat effect and arterial stiffness. *J Hypertens*, 2007; 25(4):827-831.
46. Fujita H, Matsuoka S, Awazu M. White-Coat and Reverse White-Coat Effects Correlate with 24-h Pulse Pressure and Systolic Blood Pressure Variability in Children and Young Adults. *Pediatr Cardiol*, 2016; 37(2):345-352.
47. Scuteri A, Morrell CH, Orru' M, et al. Gender specific profiles of white coat and masked hypertension impacts on arterial structure and function in the SardiNIA study. *Int J Cardiol*, 2016; 217:92-98.
48. Cuspidi C, Sala C, Tadic M, et al. Untreated masked hypertension and subclinical cardiac damage: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Am J Hypertens*, 2015; 28(6):806-813.
49. Franklin SS, Lutgarde Thijs, Hansen TW, O'Brien E, Staessen JA. White-Coat Hypertension New Insights From Recent Studies. *Hypertension*, 2013; 62:982-987.
50. Staessen JA, Asmar R, De Buyzere M, Imai Y, Parati G, Shimada K, Stergiou G, Redón J, Verdecchia P. Participants of the 2001 Consensus Conference on Ambulatory Blood Pressure Monitoring. Task Force II: blood pressure measurement and cardiovascular outcome. *Blood Press Monit*, 2001; 6:355-370.
51. Zhang H, Thijs L, Kuznetsova T, Fagard RH, Li X, Staessen JA. Progression to hypertension in the non-hypertensive participants in the Flemish Study on Environment, Genes and Health Outcomes. *J Hypertens*, 2006; 24:1719-1727.
52. Grossman E. Ambulatory blood pressure monitoring in the diagnosis and management of hypertension. *Diabetes Care*, 2013; 36(Suppl 2):S307-S311.
53. Myers MG, Valdivieso MA. Use of an automated blood pressure recording device, the BpTRU, to reduce the "white coat effect" in routine practice. *Am J Hypertens*, 2003; 16(6):494-497.
54. Cohen DL, Townsend RR. How significant is white coat hypertension? *J Clin Hypertens (Greenwich)*, 2010; 12(8):625-626.
55. Wilbert S Aronow. White Coat Hypertension. *Insights in Blood Pressure*, 2015; 1,1(6):1-3.

56. Bjorklund K, Lind L, Vessby B, Andren B, Lithell H. Different metabolic predictors of white-coat and sustained hypertension over a 20-year follow-up period: a population-based study of elderly men. *Circulation*, 2002; 106:63-68.
57. Pierdomenico SD, Cuccurullo F. Prognostic value of whitecoat and masked hypertension diagnosed by ambulatory monitoring in initially untreated subjects: an updated meta-analysis. *Am J Hypertens*, 2011; 24:52-58.
58. Stergiou GS, Asayama K, Thijs L, Kollias A, Niiranen TJ, et al. Prognosis of white-coat and masked hypertension: International Databases of Home blood pressure in relation to Cardiovascular Outcome. *Hypertension*, 2014; 63:675-682.
59. Mancia G, Bombelli M, Brambilla G, Facchetti R, Sega R, et al. Long-term prognostic value of white coat hypertension: an insight from diagnostic use of both ambulatory and home blood pressure measurements. *Hypertension*, 2013; 62:168-174.
60. Franklin SS, Thijs L, Hansen TW, et al. International Database on Ambulatory Blood Pressure in Relation to Cardiovascular Outcomes Investigators. Significance of white-coat hypertension in older persons with isolated systolic hypertension: a meta-analysis using the International Database on Ambulatory Blood Pressure Monitoring in Relation to Cardiovascular Outcomes population. *Hypertension*, 2012; 59:564-571.